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947/BPI

**IMPROVEMENT AND
DEVELOPMENT OF
INNOVATIVE PURIFICATION
TECHNIQUES OF BIOPOLYMERS
RECOVERED FROM
FERMENTATIVE BROTH**

This thesis was made at the Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant company in Ghent as a part of the Afterlife project funded from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 745737), under the guidance of prof. Božidar Šantek, PhD and with the help of ir. Thibaut Derycke.

PREFACE

Preface, a chapter that represents the end of my studies but also an end of a bigger, wonderful chapter in life. And it truly was a wonderful chapter, filled with amazing people, unslept nights spent both studying and having fun, laughter, dance, travels and uncountable adventures that student life offers to everyone who's willing to try it. And on top of that, I think the biggest adventure was this thesis. Well, the lovely thing about this thesis is that it would have never existed if there wasn't for people mentioned below. It would've been made in Germany, hopefully, in a place called Bielefeld (known as "the city that doesn't exist"). Maybe I should have recognised the hint from the start. Since that was not the case, I have to say that I can't be happier about how everything turned out in the end. It turned out with an internship in BBEPP in Ghent, falling in love with the company, work and people there, which made leaving this place kind of impossible. So, you can guess, adventure called master thesis happened there.

And here we come to the first person I'd like to say thanks. To my team leader, Thibaut, for giving me this opportunity in the first place, finding this awesome project and for being the best supervisor I could wish for. Thanks for all the advice, motivation and humour that helped me enormously with everything I did at BBEPP and of course, to make this thesis what it is now. To all the guys from my team, JJ, Matthias and Bruty for unlimited help you offered, stuff you taught me and all the fun work you gave me when I needed to clear my mind. To my Belgian family, Simo (micao), Michal and Sander, for making this place feel like a real home, everywhere we stepped our feet together. To Rakesh and Laurens, for all the great advice, fun trials (PHB pudding) and companionship in the exciting world of PHB. And to all the other amazing people from BBEPP, that I didn't mention by name, for all the knowledge you passed on, help and fun I had while working there every day.

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Now, off to new adventures! Bioprocess engineering adventures, how cool is that?!

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POBOLJŠANJE I RAZVOJ INOVATIVNIH TEHNIKA PROČIŠĆAVANJA BIOPOLIMERA IZ FERMENTIRANE PODLOGE

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Sažetak: Polihidroksialkanoati (PHA) su grupa biorazgradivih polimera proizvedenih od različitih skupina mikroorganizama. Izolacija PHA je jedan od najvažnijih faktora u dizajniranju njihove održive proizvodnje. Ovaj diplomski rad se bavio analizom različitih metoda izolacije i pročišćavanja PHA iz 3 fermentirane podloge. Tretman SDS-om, homogenizacija, kemijska razgradnja pomoću NaOH ili H₂SO₄ i završno pročišćavanje metanolom ili etanolom su odabrani kao najbolja kombinacija metoda za pročišćavanje PHA. Polihidroksibutirat (PHB) čistoće od 99,8 % s prinosom od 71,11 % je izoliran iz FB1 komine SDS tretmanom (0,025 g/g s.tv), homogenizacijom (800 bara, 2 prolaza), NaOH razgradnjom (0,025 M, 1 h, RT) i završnom obradom metanolom. PHB čistoće od 94,2 % s prinosom od 53,27 % je pročišćen iz FB2 komine SDS tretmanom (0,05 g/g s.tv.), homogenizacijom (800 bara, 2 prolaza), H₂SO₄ razgradnjom (0,7M, 6h, 90°C) i obradom metanolom. PHB čistoće od 99,2 % je izoliran iz posljednje fermentirane podloge, FB3, s prinosom od 78,3 % nakon pročišćavanja pri istim uvjetima kao i FB2, sa jedinom razlikom što je za završno pročišćavanje polimera korišten etanol.

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IMPROVEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE PURIFICATION TECHNIQUES OF BIOPOLYMERS RECOVERED FROM FERMENTATIVE BROTH

Anja Lauder, 947/BPI

Abstract: Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers produced by various microorganisms. The separation of PHAs is one of the most important key factors in the design of a sustainable PHA production. This thesis evaluated different separation methods for the recovery of polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) from three different fermentative broths. A DSP process including SDS treatment, homogenization, chemical digestion with NaOH or H₂SO₄ and methanol or ethanol polishing was selected as the best combination for the PHB recovery. PHB of 99,8 % purity was recovered from FB1 broth, with a recovery yield of 71,11 %, after 0,025 g SDS/ g DM, homogenization (800 bar, 2 passes), digestion (0,05 M NaOH, 1 h, RT) and methanol washing. PHB of 94,2 % purity was recovered from FB2 broth with a yield of 53,27 %, after 0.05 g SDS/ g DM, homogenization (800 bar, 2 passes), digestion (0,7 M H₂SO₄, 6 h, 90°C) and methanol washing. FB3 yielded PHB with a purity of 99,2 % and recovery of 78,3 %, using the same processing conditions as FB2, except it was washed with ethanol.

Keywords: Polyhydroxyalkanoates, bioplastic, purification, multistage separation procedure

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1. INTRODUCTION

Petrochemical-based polymers have become an unavoidable part of our everyday life with their wide range of applications in diverse fields such as packaging, food, agriculture, building materials, consumer products, industry, etc. Because of their resistance to chemical, physical and biological degradation, they cause serious environmental problems by increasing the difficulties of waste disposal and by promoting global warming (due to the release of carbon dioxide during incineration) (Luckachan and Pillai, 2011). Global awareness of the need to reduce plastic pollution has increased over the last years. This is now mainly done by the reduction of plastic waste (primarily by recycling), but the development of a bio based alternative would be the most fitting solution.

Biodegradable polymers, which can be obtained from renewable resources, showed great potential to replace synthetic plastic and therefore could help to resolve this world spread problem. One of the leading representatives of this group of biopolymers are polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA). PHAs are a class of linear polyesters consisting of different hydroxy acid monomers (HA) connected with an ester bond and produced intracellularly by several microorganisms as a reserve material for carbon and energy (Albuquerque and Malafaia, 2018). They have been drawing much attention lately, not only because of their biodegradability but also because of their similar material properties to conventional synthetic plastics (Jacquel et al., 2008). However, the production cost of PHA is still not competitive to their petrochemical-based counterparts. The main reasons for this are the high cost of the substrates for fermentative production (such as glucose), production in batch and fed-batch cultivation, and the large amount of solvents required for the conventional purification (Kourmentza et al., 2017). Extensive research has already been made to find an inexpensive renewable substrates for PHA production, but it's important to mention that low-cost substrates usually lead to low productivities which has a negative impact on the cost of the product recovery (Koller et al., 2017).

On the other hand, traditional purification methods use halogenated solvents for the PHA extraction which makes downstream processing expensive from the start and less safe. To make the PHA purification more sustainable and cost effective, scientists are investigating alternative methods that don't require the use of hazardous chemicals. Most of the alternative methods are based on the NPCM (non PHA cell mass) digestion with various chemicals and

enzymes or mechanical disruption of the bacterial cells. Factors such as the PHA producing strain, composition and type of PHA, purity requirements, cost and impact on PHA properties should be considered before choosing the adequate recovery method (Kosseva and Rusbandi, 2018).

The goal of this thesis will be developing cost-effective and environmentally friendly PHA purification method that will be feasible on the industrial scale and applicable even with bacterial biomass with lower PHA content. Among various reported alternative methods, this thesis will investigate the efficiency of mechanical cell disruption via homogenization, chemical digestion of NPCM (non PHA cell mass) with alkali or acid and different pellet separation methods. Optimised processing conditions will be incorporated into a complete downstream process that aims to purify PHA polymer with high recovery yields and high end product purity.

This master thesis has been made as a part of the Afterlife project that aims to develop an innovative wastewater treatment for simultaneous recovery of compounds of interest while converting the remaining organic matter into a high volumes of added value biopolymers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are a group of biopolymers - linear polyesters containing 3-hydroxy fatty acid monomers (R-3HA) connected together by an ester bond (Mozejko-Ciesielska and Kiewisz, 2016). Together with polylactic acid (PLA) and polycaprolactone (PCL), PHAs belong to the family of completely biodegradable polymers. They are water-insoluble, UV-resistant, biocompatible and non-toxic compounds with plastic-like properties (Sathya et al., 2018). PHAs are synthesized by many different types of microorganism and stored as discrete inclusion bodies in the cell cytoplasm. The PHA granule is surrounded by either phospholipids or proteins, while its size ranges between 0.2 to 0.5 μm . Depending on the type of microorganism, growth conditions and carbon source used, the molecular weight of the PHA ranges from 2×10^5 to 2×10^6 Da (Anderson and Dawes, 1990). Based on the number of carbon atoms in the monomer units, they are classified into three groups: short (scl), medium (mcl) and long-chain length (lcl) PHAs (Kunasundari and Sudesh, 2011). The scl-PHA monomers contain less than 5 carbon atoms, the most known representatives of this class are poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (P3HB) and its copolymers with 3-hydroxyvalerate (HV). Mcl-PHAs have monomers containing 5-14 carbon atoms, while lcl-PHA monomers contain more than 14 carbon atoms (Dekoning, 1995). The congeners of 3-hydroxydecanoate, 3-hydroxyoctanoate and 3-hydroxyhexanoate are examples of mcl-PHAs. The general structure and classification of PHAs is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General structure of PHAs representatives

PHAs polymers are thermoplastic and differ in their properties depending on the structural variations of monomers they are built of (homo- or copolymers) (Bugnicourt et al., 2014). All scl-PHAs are highly crystalline (60 - 80 %), and because of their brittleness and rigidity, they can cover only a part of the applications for biodegradable materials. On the other hand, mcl-PHAs have improved mechanical properties such as decreased brittleness, decreased crystallinity (25 %) and low glass transition temperature. (Raza et al., 2018). The general mechanical properties of PHA representatives are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. General properties of PHA representatives in comparison with petroleum-based plastics

PHA representative	melting temperature, T_m [°C]	glass transition temperature, T_g [°C]	Reference
P(3HB)	177-180	4	(Koller et al., 2010) (Mozejko-Ciesielska and Kiewisz, 2016)
P(3HB-co-3HV)	137-170	10 to -6	(Mozejko-Ciesielska and Kiewisz, 2016) (Koller et al., 2010)
P(4HB)	53-60	-48 to -50	(Mozejko-Ciesielska and Kiewisz, 2016)
PHA_{mcl}	45-54	-25 to -40	(Sudesh et al., 2000)
Polypropylene (PP)	176	-10	(Koller et al., 2010)
Polyethylene (PE)	130	-30	(Sudesh et al., 2000)

2.2. PHA production

PHA biosynthesis has been studied since the 1920s. Various types of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria have been found to produce different types of PHA as an energy storage material and reducing power material (Sagong et al., 2018). Together with wild microbial strains, modified yeasts and bacteria have been successfully constructed for the heterologous production of scl- and mcl-PHA (Roelants et al., 2013). PHA producing bacteria can be divided into two groups based on the stress conditions needed for the PHA synthesis. The first group are bacteria that require limitation of an essential nutrient such as N, P, Mg or S with an excess of carbon source. The main representatives of this group are *Ralstonia*

eutropha, *Protomonas extorquens* and *Protomonas oleovorans*. The second group includes bacteria that don't require growth-limiting conditions for the PHA synthesis, those are *Alcaligenes latus*, a mutant strain of *Azotobacter vinelandii* and recombinant *Escherichia coli* (Anjum et al., 2016). Beside pure culture technology and genetically modified microorganisms, PHA producing microbes can be selected from natural environment. The main principle of this approach is to engineer the ecosystem rather than bacterial strains. This strategy, called microbial community engineering (or mixed microbial consortia - MMC), doesn't require sterile substrate or sterile processing conditions, which makes it more suitable to utilize waste streams as a substrate, consequently lowering the PHA production cost (Sathya et al., 2018).

An extensive range of substrates has been used for the production of PHAs, including agricultural and household waste, industrial by-products, wastewater, lignocellulosic raw materials, fats and oils and different sugars (Anjum et al., 2016). Being one of the major costs in the PHA production, an appropriate selection of inexpensive renewable substrate is a crucial step for the commercialization of PHA. An overview of bacterial production of different PHAs, including specific bacterial strains and substrates is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. An overview of bacterial production of PHAs from renewable substrates

No.	Biopolymer	Microbial strain	Substrate	Reference
1.	P(3HB)	<i>R. eutropha</i> mRePT	lactose whey permeate	(Povolo et al., 2010)
2.	P(3HB) [P(3HB-co-HHx)]	wild type <i>R. eutropha</i> H16 <i>R. eutropha</i> Re2058/pCB113	waste animal fats	(Riedel et al., 2015)
3.	PHA	<i>R. eutropha</i> MTCC 1472	hydrolysed paddy straw	(Sandhya et al., 2013)
4.	P(3HB)	<i>Halomonas</i> sp. KM-1 <i>Burkholderia cepacia</i> ATCC 17759	waste glycerol	(Kawata and Aiba, 2010) (Zhu et al., 2010)
5.	[P(3HB-co-3HV)]	<i>Bacillus mycoides</i> DFC1	rice husk	(Narayanan et al., 2014)
6.	P(3HB) [P(3HB-co-3HHx)]	<i>R. eutropha</i> H16 <i>R. eutropha</i> PHB-4/pJRDEE32d13	soybean oil	(Kahar et al., 2004)
7.	P(3HB) and [P(HB-co-3HHx)]	<i>R. eutropha</i> H16 Re2058/pCB113	date seed oil date molasses	(Purama et al., 2018)
8.	P(3HB) and [P(3HB-co-3HV)]	<i>Comamonas</i> sp. EB172	Acetic, propionic and butyric acids derived from POME	(Zakaria et al., 2010)

9.	PHA	<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> 27N01	Fluorophenoxyalkanoic acids	(Takagi et al., 2004)
10.	P(3HB) and [P(3HB-co-4HB)]	<i>B. sacchari</i> DSM 17165	Wheat straw lignocellulosic hydrolysates (WSHs)	(Cesario et al., 2014a)
11.	[P(3HB-co-3HV)]	<i>Burkholderia cepacia</i>	Xylose and levulinic acid	(Cesario et al., 2014b)
12.	[P(3HB-co-3HV)]	Mixed microbial culture (MMC)	Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) - acetate, propionate, butyrate and valerate	(Keenan et al., 2004)
13.	PHA	<i>R. eutropha</i> ATCC 1769	VFAs - acetic, butyric, lactic and propionic acid	(Albuquerque et al., 2011)
14.	[P(3HB-co-3HV)]	<i>Burkholderia cepacia</i>	Spent coffee grounds hydrolysates (SCGH)	(Chakraborty et al., 2009)
15.	PHB	<i>Burkholderia cepacia</i> ATCC 17759	Sugar maple hemicellulosic wood hydrolysate	(Obruca et al., 2014)
16.	PHB	<i>R. eutropha</i>	Bagasse hydrolysates	(Pan et al., 2012)
17.	terpolyester [P(3HB-co-3HV-3HHx)]	<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> 4AK4 harboring genes phaAB	Mixture of dodecanoic and propionic acid	(Yu and Stahl, 2008)
18.	PHA	<i>Halomonas hydrothermalis</i> MTCC 5445	Seaweed-derived crude levulinic acid (SDCLA), containing formic acid, residual sugars and dissolved minerals	(Zhao and Chen, 2007)
19.	PHA	Recombinant <i>E. coli</i> P8-X8	Cheese whey	(Bera et al., 2015)
20.	PHA	Recombinant <i>E. coli</i> harboring phaC1 of <i>Pseudomonas. sp.</i> LDC-5	Sugar molasses	(Pais et al., 2014)
				(Saranya and Shenbagarathai, 2011)

PHA biosynthetic pathways are directly involved with central metabolic pathways including glycolytic and pentose phosphate pathways, TCA cycle and pathways for the biosynthesis and degradation of amino and fatty acids (Lu et al., 2009). The three major PHA synthesis pathways are shown in Figure 2. and they can be further engineered to encompass at least 12 pathways for the synthesis of various PHAs:

- Pathway I represents a typical scl-PHA synthesis from two acetyl-CoA,
- In the pathway II the intermediates of β -oxidation cycle are used to synthesize mcl-PHA,

- Pathway III involves fatty acid synthesis cycle that forms R-3-hydroxyacyl-CoA, which serves again as a precursor for mcl-PHA synthesis (Chen et al., 2015).

Under starvation conditions, microorganisms degrade accumulated PHAs into monomeric and/or oligomeric HAs by PHA depolymerase (PhaZ) and utilize it as an energy source (Sagong et al., 2018).

Figure 2. Major PHA biosynthetic pathways, where the key enzymes are: Acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase (PhaA), Acetoacetyl-CoA reductase (PhaB), PHA synthase (PhaC), 3-hydroxyacyl-ACP-CoA transferase (PhaG) and fatty acyl-CoA synthetase (FadD), adapted from Chen et al. (2015)

Efficient PHA production is dependent on many factors, including bacterial growth rate, cell density, percentage of PHA in cell dry weight (CDW), price of the substrates and their type. Therefore, adequate strain development, shake flask optimization, lab and pilot fermentor studies are necessary for the successful industrial scale-up (Sathya et al., 2018).

2.3. PHA purification

Since PHA granules are naturally synthesized as intracellular compounds in bacterial cytoplasm, their recovery represents one of the major bottlenecks for cost-effective production. In contrast to extracellular products, all intracellular products, including PHAs, are released from the cells by an additional purification step. In this step, all intracellular cell content will

be released together with the PHA granule content, making the starting mixture for purification less homogenous (Madkour et al., 2013). The cell content, usually called non-PHA cell mass (NPCM) or “cell residues”, mainly includes polypeptides, (phospho)lipids, DNA, RNA, and peptidoglycans (Braunegg et al., 1998).

In general, recovery methods can be divided into two groups: solvent extraction (“state of the art methods”) and alternative methods that include various types of cell disruption and NPCM digestion.

To accomplish an easier and more efficient PHA release from the cells, several pretreatment methods have been examined. Heat treatment, for example, weakens the firmness of the cell wall by denaturation of the cell proteins and destabilization of the outer membrane (Kapritchkoff et al., 2006). Other reported pretreatments include biomass grinding, drying, the use of alkali, use of sodium chloride salt solution or freezing/thawing cycles (Madkour et al., 2013). The pretreatment step can combine one or more of the methods mentioned above.

Figure 3. Common PHA recovery methods from bacterial cells, adapted from (Madkour et al., 2013)

2.3.1. Solvent extraction

The oldest and most well-established method for the PHA recovery is extraction with organic solvents. All solvent extraction methods are based on the fact that PHAs are water-insoluble, but soluble in certain types of organic solvents (Madkour et al., 2013). Most of the solvent extraction methods involve two steps, first is an increase of cell membrane permeability followed with the release and solubilization of PHA. The second step involves either solvent evaporation or precipitation of PHA with an anti-solvent (usually methanol or ethanol). Because of its simplicity and rapidity, it is commonly used in laboratory to obtain well preserved PHA of high purity (Jacquel et al., 2008). The usage of chlorinated hydrocarbon solvents such as chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane, methylene chloride or cyclic carbonates such as 1,2-propylene carbonate and ethylene carbonates is most common (Noel, 1962). Although widely used in laboratory, organic solvent extraction is not a preferred method for pilot or industrial scale because it is not environmentally friendly, requires high capital and operational costs and it is potentially harmful for the operators (Kunasundari and Sudesh, 2011).

To make extraction process more sustainable and avoid the use of hazardous chemicals, scientists have investigated the use of non-halogenated solvents. According to Mantelatto and Duraó (2008) extraction of PHAs can be performed using isoamyl alcohol (3-methyl-1-butanol), amyl acetate or fusel oil (mixture of high alcohols). Another purification method that combines extraction and filtration has been reported by Horowitz (2000) where PHAs were simultaneously extracted with acetone and separated from cells and cell debris via filtration. Moreover, acetone extraction was successfully applied on industrial scale, after which PHA was precipitated with mixture of methanol and ethanol (Elbahloul and Steinbuhel, 2009). A similar large-scale process was performed using ethyl-acetate as an extraction solvent for P(3HB-co-3HHx), after which hexane or heptane was used to precipitate the polymer (Chen et al., 2001). Other reported non-halogenated solvents that could be used for PHA extraction are lactic acid esters (Metzner, 1998), acetic acid anhydride, n-methyl-pyrrolidone and tetrahydrofuran (Furrer et al., 2008).

2.3.2. Alternative methods for PHA purification

Over the last few years, the interest for alternative PHA purification methods that could replace the traditional halogenated solvent extraction strongly increased. This can make

downstream processing more sustainable, safe and environmentally friendly. Various reported alternative PHA recovery methods are shown in Table 3. The focus was put on different digestion methods where, instead of the PHA granules, NPCM is solubilized, leaving PHA granules intact. Solubilization of the NPCM can be achieved by using either chemicals or enzymes.

Different chemicals can be used to convert hydrophilic components of the NPCM into water-soluble substances which can be separated by filtration, centrifugation or flotation. In case of scl-PHA, separation is easier due to their higher density (around 1,2 g/mL) which improves their sedimentation in the water phase. Contrary to scl-PHA, mcl-PHA have a density similar to water (around 1 g/mL), which is why ultracentrifugation or cross-flow filtration is required for their efficient separation (Koller et al., 2013).

Sodium hypochlorite is frequently used as an oxidizing agent for degradation of polymeric NPCM, whereas PHA is mostly resistant and doesn't dissolve in the hypochlorite solution. To avoid molecular weight reduction of isolated PHA, operational conditions such as initial biomass concentration, pH and digestion time have to be optimized (Berger, 1989). Hypochlorite digestion can also be used in combination with chloroform, where cell pellets are lysed by hypochlorite and PHA simultaneously extracted with chloroform. In this method, chloroform partially protects PHA from further degradation by hypochlorite after it has been released from bacterial cells (Hahn et al., 1994).

PHA recovery can also be achieved with surfactants such as sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS). SDS disintegrates the cell wall by incorporating itself into the lipid bilayer of the cytoplasmic membrane, thus, releasing the PHA and finally solubilizing the NPCM. To increase the recovery rate and purity of PHA, agents such as sodium hydroxide or hypochlorite have to be added (Jacquel et al., 2008). Moreover, SDS treatment can be combined with mechanical disruption methods such as homogenization. The main disadvantage of SDS treatment is its high-cost and difficult removal from the wastewater. To reduce the required amount of SDS, treatment has to be combined with different purification methods.

Acidic or alkaline NPCM digestion represents an attractive alternative recovery method because it is considered more economically feasible and environmentally friendly. Alkaline treatment with NaOH causes hydrolysis and saponification of proteins and lipopolysaccharides. This makes the cell membrane partially permeable and induces the protein and PHA release from the cell (Anis et al., 2013). In contrast to alkaline digestion, acids such as H₂SO₄ degrade the bacterial cells by disintegration of peptidoglycan, releasing the protein and other biological macromolecules into the aqueous solution (Lopez-Abelairas et al., 2015).

The resistance of PHA against degradation by protons and hydroxyl anions differs. The major monomeric, water-soluble products of PHB hydrolysis are 3-hydroxybutyric acid (3-HB) and crotonic acid (CA) (Tapadiya and Vasanthan, 2017). Yu et al. (2005) investigated the difference in the PHB hydrolysis mechanism in alkaline and acidic conditions. They reported that the marginal hydrolysis of the polymer occurred in the sulphuric acid solutions of 0,05 – 2 M at 80°C for more than 14 h. In contrast, hydroxyl anions attacked the PHB backbone efficiently at a concentration ranging from 0,1 - 4 M, even at mild processing conditions (at RT, incubation time lower than 2 h). They reported that hydroxyl anions can lower the energy barrier of the ester bond breakage. Once the ester bond is split into carboxylic acid and alcohol, OH⁻ can remove protons from the produced acid. In that way, the re-esterification between formed acids and alcohols is prevented. Since hydroxyl anion is a reagent in this case, high NaOH concentrations promote the rate of PHB hydrolysis. On the other hand, they found a dynamic balance between breakage and repair of ester bonds in the moderate acidic conditions. Different from hydroxyl anions, protons from the acid are the catalyst for both hydrolysis and esterification. Therefore, broken ester bond between newly formed carboxylic acid and alcohol can be repaired.

For all those reasons mentioned above, alkaline digestions showed better PHB recoveries when they were performed on temperatures lower than 30°C and with shorter incubation time due. Besides NaOH concentration, the degree of PHB crystallinity plays an important role in the polymer hydrolysis rate (Yu and Chen, 2006). They revealed that the crystallization of native PHB granules occurs even with a partial protein removal. This happens during the NPCM dissolution when proteins involved in granule stabilization are removed and protons facilitate the crystallization. The amorphous structure of PHB in the original cell mass changes to the highly crystalline and in that state, PHB crystals are highly resistant to alkaline/chemical digestion. As a result, chemical digestion parameters have to be carefully optimised to avoid polymer degradation. Both alkaline and acidic treatment result in high PHA purity (Table 3.) if optimal conditions are applied. Because of this and because of the low cost of the process, these methods are applicable on industrial scale.

Apart from chemicals, various purified enzymes or crude enzyme extracts can be used for the NPCM digestion. The advantages of enzymatic disruption lie in its specificity, aqueous recovery and mild operational conditions. However, industrial application is difficult due to the high-cost of enzymes and general complexity of the recovery process. Proteases, nucleases, lysozyme and lipases are commonly used enzymes for the cell lysis (Madkour et al., 2013). A

polymer purity above 95 % can be achieved if an optimised combination of enzymatic cocktails, heat treatment and surfactants is used (Koller et al., 2013).

Besides NPCM digestion, mechanical disruption of bacterial biomass is a widely used method for the recovery of intracellular compounds, including PHA. Among the various mechanical disruption methods, high pressure homogenization (HPH) and bead milling are regularly used in the industrial scale cell disruption. With HPH, disruption of the cell suspension occurs under high pressure through an adjustable homogenizing valve. For efficient cell disruption, process parameters such as operating pressure, number of passes and biomass concentration have to be carefully selected. Poor cell disruption occurs at low biomass concentrations, for this reason, fermented broth has to be concentrated before homogenization (Tamer et al., 1998). Disruption performance also depends on the microbial physiology. Generally, Gram-positive bacteria are more difficult to disrupt than Gram-negative due to the difference in the composition of their cell wall. When homogenization is performed in combination with NaOH and SDS treatment, degree of cell disruption on *C. necator* can even exceed 99 % (Koller et al., 2013). The principle of bead mills is based on the shearing forces and energy transfer from beads to cells in the contact zones. Contrary to HPH, its performance is independent of the biomass concentration but, depends on the bead loading (Jacquel et al., 2008). Although the additional use of chemicals is not required for efficient disruption, it is not commonly used in industry because it is difficult to scale-up.

Supercritical fluids (SCF) have appeared as a potential PHA recovery method. SCF are described as substances that are at a temperature and pressure above their critical point, where distinct gas and liquid phases do not exist. Their unique physicochemical properties such as high density and low viscosity make them suitable extraction solvents. Being an inexpensive, fast and environmentally friendly method, SCF have gained much popularity over the last few years (Kunasundari and Sudesh, 2011). Among different types of SCF, CO₂ is most broadly used because of its low toxicity and reactivity, moderate critical temperature and pressure (31°C, 73 bar), low cost and nonflammability (Hejazi et al., 2003). Although SCF efficiency is comparable to other alternative methods, bacterial cell disruption with SC-CO₂ is highly dependent on operating pressure, temperature, type of modifier (Kunasundari and Sudesh, 2011) and culture cultivation time, which makes process optimisation quite demanding (Khosravi-Darani et al., 2004).

Dissolved-air flotation was investigated for the recovery of PHA inclusion bodies from *Pseudomonas putida* after the enzymatic treatment with lysozyme and Novozyme A. It has been reported that isoelectric points of PHA and cell debris were practically the same, around

pH 3,5, near which selective aggregation and then flotation can be performed. The main disadvantage of this method is that it requires several consecutive flotation steps for efficient PHA recovery (Van Hee et al., 2004).

Another potential PHA recovery method that has been recently reported is aqueous two-phase system (ATPS). ATPS is formed when two incompatible polymers at low concentrations (or one polymer and an inorganic salt) are mixed such that two immiscible phases coexist. Low process time, low material cost and energy consumption, high yield and easy scale-up make this method an attractive alternative to conventional methods (Yang et al., 2008). Factors such as polymer molecular weight, polymer and salt concentration, pH and charge have to be considered when choosing an adequate ATPS recovery system. However, ATPS is still not being used at the industrial scale because of its low reproducibility and poor understanding of the mechanism (Kunasundari and Sudesh, 2011).

Organic solvents such as ethanol and methanol can be used for polishing of the recovered polymer. These short chain alcohols were found to solubilize the residual NPCM, mostly by extracting grease and lipid cell debris, while the polymer stays intact (Anis et al., 2013). Anis et al. (2012) reported the copolymer P(3HB-co-3HHx) purity increase by 5 % after washing the digested broth with 20 % (v/v) ethanol in pellet to solvent ratio of 1:20.

Table 3. Various alternative PHA recovery methods

Digestion method	Chemical used	Strain	Conditions	Purity	Reference
Sodium hypochlorite	NaOCl	<i>C. necator</i> DSM 545	30°C, 1 h	98 %	(Berger et al., 1989)
Surfactant	SDS	Recombinant <i>E. coli</i>	5 % w/v, 37°C, 1h	99 %	(Choi and Lee, 1999)
Surfactant-NaOCl	Triton X-100-NaOCl	<i>C. necator</i> DSM 545	n.a.	98 %	(Chavarie, 1990)
Dispersion of sodium hypochlorite and chloroform	Chloroform - NaOCl	<i>C. necator</i> , Recombinant <i>E. coli</i>	20 % (v/v) NaOCl, 30°C, 1 h	>98 %	(Hahn et al., 1995)
Selective dissolution by acid	H ₂ SO ₄	<i>C. necator</i> H16	3,5 % (v/v), 80°C, 6 h	99 %	(Lopez-Abelairas et al., 2015)
Selective dissolution by alkali	NaOH	Recombinant <i>E. coli</i>	0,1 M, 30°C, 1 h	91-92 %	(Choi and Lee, 1999)

		<i>Commamonas sp. EB172</i>	0,05 M, 4°C, 1 h	88,6 %	(Mohammadi et al., 2012)
		Mixed culture	0,2 M, 30°C, 3 h	93 %	(Jiang et al., 2015)
Enzymatic digestion	Enzyme combined with SDS-EDTA	<i>P. putida</i>	n.a.	93 %	(Yasothea et al., 2006)
Mechanical disruption	Bead mill	<i>Alicyobacterium latus</i>	Bead diameter of 512 µm, bead loading of 85 %, 2800 rpm	99 %	(Tamer et al., 1998)
Mechanical disruption	High pressure homogenization	<i>Methylobacterium sp V49</i>	5 % SDS, 400 bar, 2 passes	95 %	(Ghatnekar et al., 2002)
Supercritical fluid (SCF)	SC-CO ₂	<i>C. necator</i>	Supercritical CO ₂ , 100 min, 200 atm, 40°C and 0,2 ml of methanol	89 %	(Hejazi et al., 2003)
Dissolved-air flotation	Enzymatic hydrolysis, sonification, flotation	<i>P. putida</i>		86 %	(Van Hee et al., 2006)
Aqueous two-phase system (ATPS)	Polyethylene glycol [PEG] 8000/phosphate	<i>B. flexus</i>	pH 8,0 28°C, 30 min	95 %	(Divyashree et al., 2009)

2.4. Analytical methods for PHA quantification

2.4.1. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis has been extensively used for various polymer identification and characterisation. Hahn and Chang (1995) have developed an analytical method for the determination of the PHB content using TGA. By comparing gas chromatography (GC) and TGA results of the same samples, they observed a linear PHB content overestimation in TGA results due to the spontaneous NPCM degradation in samples with higher NPCM content. The correlation of PHB contents determined by TGA and GC is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The correlation of PHB contents determined by TGA and GC analysis (Hahn and Chang, 1995)

Besides quantifying the PHB purity, TGA can be used for the determination of thermal stability of the PHB. Mamat et al. (2014) compared the degradation temperature of pure PHB and PHB integrated in the bacterial biomass. They reported that the degradation temperature of pure PHB samples was shifted to lower temperatures in comparison with the crude PHB integrated in the bacterial biomass. Beside the change in molecular weight that can occur during PHB processing, they concluded that the difference may also be due to limitation in thermal diffusion in samples containing more cell debris.

2.5. Patent research and future perspectives for sustainable PHA production

In comparison with widely used petroleum-based plastics such as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE), the estimated PHA production cost is 3-4 times higher (Koller, 2017). Even though several companies have managed to industrialize the PHA production (Figure 5.), there are still obstacles that need to be surpassed in order to achieve the wanted goal. First of all, production cost should be lowered, secondly, high value-added applications of PHA should be found. Thirdly, the integration of PHA based materials as commodity will take an adaptation of the current industrial standard.

Name of Company	Product (Trademark)	Substrate	Biocatalyst	Production Capacity
Biomatera, Canada	PHA resins (Biomatera)	Renewable raw materials	Non-pathogenic, non-transgenic bacteria isolated from soil	
Biomer, Germany	PHB pellets (Biomer [®])	Sugar (sucrose)		
Bio-On Srl., Italy	PHB, PHBV spheres (minerv [®] -PHA)	Sugar beets	<i>Cupriavidus necator</i>	10,000 t/a
BluePHA, China	Customized PHBVHHx, PHV, P3HP3HB, P3HP4HB, P3HP, P4HB synthesis		Development of microbial strains via synthetic biology	
Danimer Scientific, USA Kaneka Corporation, Japan	mcl-PHA (Nodax [®] PHA) PHB-PHHx (AONILEX [®])	Cold pressed canola oil Plant oils		3500 t/a
Newlight Technologies LLC, USA	PHA resins (AirCarbon TM)	Oxygen from air and carbon from captured methane emissions	Newlight's 9X biocatalyst	
PHB Industrial S.A., Brazil	PHB, PHBV (BIOCYLE [®])	Saccharose	<i>Alcaligenes</i> sp.	3000 t/a
PolyFerm, Canada	mcl-PHA (VersaMer TM PHA)	Sugars, vegetable oils	Naturally selected microorganisms	
Shenzhen Ecomann Biotechnology Co. Ltd., China	PHA pellets, resins, microbeads (Ambio [®])	Sugar or glucose		5000 t/a
SIRIM Bioplastics Pilot Plant, Malaysia	Various types of PHA	Palm oil mill effluent (POME), crude palm kernel oil		2000 t/a
TianAn Biologic Materials Co. Ltd., China	PHB, PHBV (ENMAT TM)	Dextrose deriving from corn of cassava grown in China	<i>Ralstonia eutropha</i>	10,000 t/a, 50,000 t/a by 2020
Tianjin GreenBio Material Co., China	P (3, 4HB) films, pellets/foam pellets (Sogreen [®])	Sugar		10,000 t/a

PHB, P3HB: poly(3-hydroxybutyrate); PHBV: poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate); PHBVHHx: poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate-co-3-hydroxyhexanoate); PHV: poly-3-hydroxyvalerate; P3HP3HB: poly(3-hydroxypropionate-co-3-hydroxybutyrate); P3HP4HB: poly(3-hydroxypropionate-co-4-hydroxybutyrate); P3HP: poly(3-hydroxypropionate); P4HB: poly(4-hydroxybutyrate); mcl-PHA: medium-chain length PHA; P(3,4HB): poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-4-hydroxybutyrate).

Figure 5. Pilot and industrial scale PHA manufacturers active worldwide (Koller, 2017)

To lower the PHA production cost, researchers are trying to achieve high cell density growth of PHA producing strains within a short period of time, induce controllable lysis of PHA containing cells, make PHA composition controllable, produce large PHA granules for easy separation and in general, find an environmentally friendly and affordable way of PHA purification. Also, continuous fermentation and potential PHA producing plants have been investigated (Chen, 2009). Besides lowering the production cost, finding value-added applications of PHA such as bio-implant materials, as fine chemicals and drugs and as compounds for specific drug delivery has been investigated (Chen, 2011).

Over the last 10 years, worldwide interest in PHA production has been continually increasing. This is visible in Figure 6., which shows the number of published patents over the past 10 years on the given subject. PHA research leading countries are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Number of new patent publications from 2010 until the April, 2019. (Derwent, 2019)

Figure 7. PHA patent research leading countries in April 2019. (Derwent, 2019)

Most of the active patents regarding the alternative PHA recovery methods are published in the United States. They describe industrial purification processes for PHAs that consist of various combinations of mechanical pretreatment and disruption of microbial biomass, acid or alkali pretreatment, enzymatic pretreatment, addition of flocculants or surfactants and washing with low carbon alcohols (Chen, 2009; Yanagita et al., 2008; Hollmann et al., 2011). Since most of the patents give generalized ideas and protocols for sustainable PHA purification, optimization and development is necessary in order to create a cost-effective, reproducible process that would help in making PHA competitive on the world market.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. General content

3.1.1. Chemicals

During the experimental part of this thesis certain chemicals and equipment were used, those are listed up in Table 4. and chapter 3.1.2.

Table 4. List of chemicals

Chemical	Supplier
Benzoic acid ≥ 99.5 %	Merck chemicals, India
Chloroform (stabilised with 0,6% ethanol)	VWR Chemicals, France
Ethanol (absolute)	VWR Chemicals, France
Methanol	VWR Chemicals, France
Poly (3-hydroxybutyric acid-co-3-hydroxyvaleric acid) (PHV content 12 mol %)	Merck chemicals, USA
Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)	Fisher Scientific, Belgium
Sodium hydroxide	Honeywell Research Chemicals, Germany
Sulphuric acid (96 %)	VWR Chemicals, France

3.1.2. Equipment

- Analytical balance (Ohaus Corporation, USA)
- 4-piston diaphragm pump (QF1000, Quattroflow Fluid Systems, Germany)
- Centrifuge (5427 R, Eppendorf, Germany)
- Centrifuge (Heraeus Multifuge X3R, ThermoFisher Scientific, USA)
- GC-MS (Interscience, USA)

- Heating plate (Hei-Tec, Heidolph, Germany)
- Lab ceramic filter unit (Tami industries, France)
- Lab homogenizer (Panda Plus 1000, Italy)
- Magnetic stirrer (L23, Labinco, Netherlands)
- Orbital shaker (Innova 44 R, Infors ecotron, Innova 4230, New Brunswick 42 R)
- pH meter (Hanna Instruments, Belgium)
- Sartorius moisture analyser (MA-37-1, Germany)
- Technical balance (Pioneer, Ohaus Corporation, USA)
- Thermogravimetric analyser (TGA Q-500, TA Instruments, USA)
- Thermo mixer (Eppendorf, Germany)
- Vortex (3, IKA, Germany)

3.2. Analytical methods

3.2.1. GC-MS

PHA identification was determined using the GC-MS method adapted from (Oehmen et al., 2005) that was originally proposed by (Braunegg et al., 1978). The derivatization method involved hydrolysis of the polymer and conversion to a methyl-ester of the monomeric 3-hydroxyalkanoate (3HA) fraction (Figure 8.). Methyl-esters of 3-HA were extracted with chloroform and analysed via GC-MS.

Figure 8. Schematic diagram of derivatization method for PHB analysis, based on Oehmen et al. (2005) method

All samples were derivatized using the same protocol. ± 5 mg of an external standard (PHB/HV was used as an external standard) or dried sample was weighed and put in 1,5 mL

glass vial. 0,75 mL of chloroform was added together with 0,75 mL of acidified methanol (3 % v/v sulphuric acid) containing 1 mg/ml of benzoic acid to the glass vial after which the vial was tightly sealed with the crimp cap. Prepared samples were heated at 100°C for 3 h in a Thermomixer. After the reaction was finished, samples were cooled in cold water and then 0,5 mL of RO-water was added to enhance the phase separation. After the addition of water, samples were vigorously shaken and centrifuged to obtain fast phase separation. The organic phase (bottom phase) was transferred to GC-vial for analysis.

GC-MS system incorporated ZB-5ms column, Thermo electron Trace DSQ MS detector and CTC A200S Liquid sampler. The MS was run in scan mode at a detector voltage of 1,0 kV in the mass range of 50-650 amu. The scan speed and interval were 500 amu/s and 1.22 s. The oven temperature was set to 40°C for 1 min, increased at 10°C min to 250°C.

3.2.2. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Samples were centrifuged and the pellet was left to dry in the lab oven at 60°C until a constant mass was observed. The sample was grinded into powder prior to thermogravimetric analysis. The TGA method for PHB quantification was adapted from Hahn and Chang (1995). Around 10 mg of each sample was placed on a platinum pan. The heating rate was set to 10°C/min from 50°C to 200°C, 5°C/min from 200-300°C, pyrolysis was kept isothermal for 5 min and then finally continued 10°C/min from 300-400°C. N₂ was used as a drying gas during the TG analysis. PHB content was described as the % of rapid weight loss during the thermal degradation between 200 and 290°C, corrected with Hahn and Chang (1995) correlation shown in Figure 4. All results were calculated as mean of duplicate tests. Recovery yield (%) was calculated after each individual processing step using equation shown below.

$$\text{Recovery yield (\%)} = \frac{m(\text{PHB after purification step})[\text{g}]}{m(\text{PHB before purification step})[\text{g}]} * 100 \%$$

3.2.3. Dry matter measurement

The dry matter content was measured with a Sartorius moisture analyser (Figure 9.). Every sample (2 g) was heated at 105°C in the analyser until constant mass was reached. The dry

matter (DM %S) content was calculated by dividing the final mass by the starting sample mass and multiplying by 100.

Figure 9. Sartorius moisture analyser (MA-37-1)

3.3. Experimental methods used for PHA isolation and purification

3.3.1. Chloroform PHB extraction from bacterial biomass

Chloroform extraction was used as a control method for the isolation of PHB from bacterial cells. The protocol was based on the previously defined method by Mozumder et al. (2014). Figure 10. shows the successive steps with the in- and outgoing streams.

Figure 10. Chloroform extraction flowchart

1,5 g of the wet bacterial pellet was mixed with 20 mL of chloroform at room temperature for 48 h. After the extraction, cellular debris was separated by filtration (Borosilicate filter, porosity 1). PHB in the filtrate was precipitated with 20 mL of ice-cold ethanol (absolute) and separated by centrifugation. The extraction procedure was repeated twice. The separated PHB pellets were left to dry at room temperature.

3.3.2. Alternative PHB purification methods

Potential alternative PHB purification methods were chosen and evaluated during the practical part of this thesis. The examined downstream processing steps are showed in Figure 11.

3.3.2.1. SDS treatment

Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) was added to the broth prior to homogenization in different concentrations to evaluate the difference in cell disruption efficiency. Dry matter (DM %S) of well mixed broth was measured using a Sartorius moisture analyser. SDS was added to 100 mL of broth in following concentrations: 0, 0,025, 0,05 and 0,1 g SDS/ g DM. SDS containing broths were mixed on a magnetic stirrer plate for 1 h before the homogenization step.

3.3.2.2. Homogenization

100 mL of broth treated with different concentrations of SDS (or un-treated) was disrupted using the GEA Panda lab homogenizer (Figure 12.). The cell disruption was evaluated at 400 and 800 bar, with 1, 2 or 4 broth passages. The homogenized samples were centrifuged using a ThermoFisher lab centrifuge (Figure 13.) for 5 min at 4700 g. The supernatant was discarded and pellets were washed with RO-water, with the same volume as supernatant. The washing step was repeated twice (until the supernatant was visually colourless). The washed pellets were left to dry at 60°C after which they were analysed on TGA for PHA content. The homogenization efficiency was evaluated by the increase of PHA content in dry pellets due to the release of soluble cell particles.

Figure 12. Lab homogenizer GEA Niro Soavi's PandaPLUS 2000

Figure 13. Lab centrifuge (Heraeus Multifuge X3R, ThermoFisher Scientific)

3.3.2.3. Pellets separation methods

The homogenized broth samples and samples after the chemical digestion were poured in 50 mL falcons and centrifuged for 1 min at 4700 g. If pellets weren't stable, centrifugation time was increased.

Ultrafiltration was performed on a lab ceramic filter unit (Figure 14.) equipped with a 7 channel membrane with a pore size of 300 kDa (Tami industries, Figure 15.). 2 L of broth was filtrated after homogenization and after chemical digestion. After both filtrations, diafiltration was performed with RO water until visually colourless filtrate was obtained.

Figure 14. Lab scale ceramic filter unit

Figure 15. Ceramic membrane (300 kDa, Tami industries)

3.3.2.4. NPCM dissolution with NaOH or H₂SO₄

The first stage screening of NPCM dissolution with NaOH or H₂SO₄ was evaluated on un-treated fermentation broths using different conditions (Figure 16.). The digested broths were centrifugated (4700g, 5 min), the supernatant was discarded and the DM %S of the wet pellets were determined. The wet biomass was weighted, transferred into a falcon and mixed with acid

or base of a specified concentration. To reach 4 % of dry matter in the final mixture, mass of each digestion solution was calculated as it follows:

$$m(\text{digestion solution})[g] = \frac{m(\text{wet pellet})[g] * \frac{DM(\text{wet pellet})[\%S]}{100}}{0,04}$$

Chemical digestion was performed in a Thermomixer or using an orbital shaker if the digestion conditions were tested at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C). After chemical digestion with sulphuric acid, for certain samples pH was adjusted to 10 using 5 M or 0,5 M NaOH to test the impact on PHB recovery and the precipitation efficiency. After the chemical digestion, samples were centrifuged (4700 g, 20 min) and the supernatant was discarded. Pellets were washed twice with RO-water after which they were put to dry at 60 °C prior to TGA and GC-MS analysis.

Figure 16. Chemical conditions tested in the 1st screening

For the second stage screening, conditions that gave the best results were chosen and chemical digestion was performed with washed bacterial pellets after SDS treatment and homogenization. The best condition of both acidic and alkali digestion together was tested.

After the second stage screening, the final repetition of the best condition combination was performed and samples with recovered polymer were analysed.

3.3.2.5. Short-chain alcohol polishing

Short-chain alcohols such as ethanol and methanol were selected for polymer polishing. The wet washed pellet after chemical digestion was mixed with solvent in pellet to solvent ratio of 1:20 for 3 h at RT. The solution was then centrifuged (4700 g, 10 min) and the solvent phase (supernatant) was discarded. The pellet was then washed with RO-water, in a water to pellet ratio of 1:20, and left to dry at 60 °C until constant mass.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. General content

Three different fermentative broths containing PHB were used for the evaluation and development of downstream processing method. For easier follow up, they were labelled as FB1, FB2 and FB3. The main differences between processed broths are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Fermentative broth characteristics

Broth label	Bacterial strain	Carbon source	Broth state	Amount of broth available	PHA type	PHA content (%)
FB1	<i>Paraburkholderia sacchari</i>	glucose	pasteurised fresh broth (1h at 60°C), 4 % of DM	20 L	PHB	64,0
FB2	Modified strain of <i>Cupriavidus necator</i>	volatile fatty acids	freeze-dried biomass	800 g	PHB	26,8
FB3	Mixed culture	volatile fatty acids	frozen biomass, 11 % of DM	30 g	PHB	45,4

An extensive screening of the conditions of each downstream processing step was performed on FB1 and FB2. Due to the low quantity available of FB3 (Table 5.), the best processing conditions of both were chosen and tested on FB3. Prior to DSP steps evaluation, freeze-dried cells of FB2 and defrosted FB3 cells were resuspended in RO-water to obtain a broth solution of similar DM (%) content as it was after the fermentation. However, the composition of FB2 and FB3 was different from FB1, because the supernatant after centrifugation of the fermentation broth was replaced with RO water.

4.2. Characterization of fermentation broth with different analytical methods

In order to identify the PHA type and determine the PHA content in each fermentation broth, GC-MS and thermogravimetric analysis were used. (previously described in chapters 3.2.1 and 3.2.2.)

4.2.1. GC-MS

PHA identification in different fermentation broths was performed using GC-MS with the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST02) database. In order to remove the background noise, the base spectrum before and after the peak was manually subtracted. After searching the database, the closest spectra match in the NIST02 database was recorded (chemical formula, molecular weight and NIST number) together with a match factor (shown as a percentage). The chromatogram of P(3HB-c-3HV) standard is shown in Figure 17a, together with its library record (Figure 17b). Chromatograms of the different starting fermentation broths are shown in appendix (chapter 2.)

Figure 17a. GC-MS chromatogram of P(3HB-c-3HV) standard showing 3-HB, 3-HV and benzoic acid peak

Figure 17b. 3-hydroxybutyric methyl ester (3-HB) peak identification record

4.2.1. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

PHB was extracted using the chloroform method (described in chapter 3.3.1.) from both FB1 and FB2. The extracts were analysed on TGA Q-500 and used as a standard. During thermogravimetric analysis, it was found that PHB is rapidly degrading in the range of 200 to 290°C (A, Figure 18.). NPCM degradation (B, Figure 18.) started between 250 – 300 °C and it was fully degraded at 500 °C. (Figure 15.). Looking at the thermal degradation profile of FB1 and FB2, one can see that the degradation of FB1 started at lower temperatures, despite having a higher PHB content (Figure 18.) . When poly(3-hydroxybutyric acid-co-3-hydroxyvaleric acid) standard was analysed, only one peak was detected (Figure 18.). This was in correlation with Hahn and Chang (1995) that reported a single peak for the PHB/V copolymer degradation. Since it was not possible to distinguish between various types of PHA, TGA was used for the fast determination of PHB content (% w/w) in the processed samples.

Figure 18. Thermogram of PHB extracted with chloroform from FB1 and FB2, overlaid with the P(3HB-c-3HV) standard

Besides the PHB content, TG analysis was used for the evaluation of the thermal stability of PHB in the processed samples. A decrease in degradation temperature was observed and explained as a change in PHB characteristics, i.e. reduction of molecular weight. A similar conclusion was reported by (Mamat et al., 2014). This can lead to the conclusion that the shorter PHB polymer will be thermally less stable.

4.3. Homogenization

Since PHB is produced as an intracellular product, cell disruption is necessary for its release from the cells. Among the various cell disruption methods, high-pressure homogenization was chosen because of its scalability, economic advantages and mild damage to the processed products (Tamer et al., 1998). Different homogenization conditions were first evaluated on FB1 broth, after which the homogenization performance of the developed conditions was applied and compared for FB2 and FB3.

4.3.1. SDS induced cell disruption prior to homogenization

SDS was added to FB1 and FB2 prior to homogenization in different concentrations to test whether it improves cell disruption efficiency. Many articles reported better disruption when SDS was added in concentrations between 1-5 % w/v (Ghatnekar et al., 2002). Since high amounts of SDS increase production costs and cause foaming while processing, lower concentrations were tested (Table 6.).

Homogenization efficiency was evaluated by analysing the PHB content in dry pellet after the homogenization. By cause of cell breakage, water-soluble cell particles (i.e. proteins, nucleic acids) moved to the aqueous phase and were easily separated by centrifugation in the supernatant. Since PHB is insoluble in water, removal of soluble cell particles caused the increase of PHB content in the remaining pellet. The results of cell disruption via homogenization, with and without SDS are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Cell disruption via homogenization

Broth type	DM (%S)	Pressure (bar)	g SDS /g DM	Before disruption	No of passages		
					1	2	4
FB1	5,5	400	0	64,0	64,9	70,9	72,2
		800	0		70,5	74,7	75,5
			0,025		73,2	77,8	-
			0,05		71,1	75,0	-
			0,1		72,0	73,8	-
FB2	6,34	800	0	26,8	27,8	30,8	29,7
			0,025		28,1	29,9	32,2
			0,05		29,3	33,2	31,0
			0,1		-	-	-

Since higher PHB release was observed after the homogenization of FB1 at 800 bar, the evaluation was continued only at this pressure. Increased PHB concentrations were observed after one passage at 800 bar for both FB1 and FB2, without the addition of SDS, whereas the best results were obtained after 2 homogenization passes. Since there was no significant difference between 2 and 4 passes, SDS evaluation was continued without homogenization with 4 broth passes. SDS treatment improved the cell disruption efficiency in all samples. The addition of 0,025 g SDS/ g DM to FB1 showed the highest increase in PHB content. In comparison with the reference method (broth homogenized at 800 bar with 1 pass), the PHB content was 13,8 % higher. For the FB2, addition of 0,05 g SDS / g DM showed the best result, PHB content increased for 6,4 %. This distinction between the required amount of SDS is most probably caused by the difference in physiology of two bacterial strains.

4.4. Chemical digestion

4.4.1. First stage screening of chemical digestion with NaOH

Aqueous solutions of NaOH were found to have a high potential in dissolving the NPCM of bacterial cells (Anis et al., 2013). Based on the best results reported in the literature review, chemical digestion was performed with NaOH in concentrations between 0,05-0.5 M,

for 1 – 4 h, at temperatures varying from 25 – 40 °C. The first evaluation of chosen conditions was performed on FB1, with a focus on thermal stability of the recovered PHB. These results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Effect of different digestion conditions with NaOH on PHB extraction from FB1 with the initial PHB content of 64,0 % and 4 % of solids in digestion solution

Chemical digestion	FB1	NaOH concentration			
		0,05 M	0,1 M	0,2 M	0,5 M
Digestion temperature [°C]	Digestion time [h]	PHB content (%)			
RT	1	65,7	67,6	72,5	85,9
	2	67,7	65,6	71,2	85,1
	4	66,7	62,3	69,8	85,2
40°C	1	64,3	60,3	58,9	88,1
	2	66,0	75,6	77,8	84,3

The PHB concentration in the pellet increased with increased NaOH concentration. The increase in digestion time did not have much impact on NPCM digestion. PHB content did not change significantly with higher incubation times. This was in correlation with (Lopez-Abelairas et al., 2015) and (Mohammadi et al., 2012). As for the thermal stability of purified PHB, NaOH concentrations above 0,1 M had a negative impact on the polymer stability. Their PHB degradation temperature was lower compared to the both of the PHB standards extracted with chloroform. The degradation temperature decreased with the increase of NaOH concentration. The correlation between the degradation temperature of PHB and NaOH concentration is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. NaOH concentration impact on thermal stability of PHB

Increasing the digestion temperature from RT to 40 °C did not show significant improvement on NPCM digestion (Table 7.). A similar result was observed by (Mohammadi et al., 2012) when isolating P(3HB-co-3HV) from *Comamonas sp.* EB172. They reported the highest purity and recovery rates when digestion was performed at lower temperatures (4°C) due to improved PHA precipitation. For that reason, lower digestion temperatures with decreased digestion time were tested on FB2. The results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Effect of lower digestion temperature with NaOH on PHB extraction from FB2 with an initial PHB content of 26.8 % and 4 % of solids in the digestion solution

		NaOH concentration			
Chemical digestion	FB2	0,05 M	0,075 M	0,1 M	0,2 M
Digestion temperature [°C]	Digestion time [h]	PHB content (%)			
RT	1	29,0	32,4	51,2	68,7
5	1	42,6	45,1	53,3	51,5
15	1	29,8	40,9	48,6	50,0

Decreased digestion temperature did not have much impact on improvement of polymer recovery, as well as its thermal stability. The best results for both FB1 and FB2 were obtained with digestion at RT for 1 h, for that reason, the second stage screening was performed under those conditions.

4.4.2. First stage screening of chemical digestion with H₂SO₄

Because of the acidic digestion advantages over alkali that were thoroughly explained in the literature review, digestion with H₂SO₄ was tested on untreated FB1 and FB2 broth.

Table 9. Effect of different digestion conditions with H₂SO₄ on PHB extraction from FB1 with the initial PHB content of 64,0 %, with 4 % of solids in digestion solution and without pH adjustment after digestion.

		H ₂ SO ₄ concentration			
Chemical digestion	FB1	0,05 M	0,1 M	0,2 M	0,5 M
Digestion temperature [°C]	Digestion time [h]	PHB content (%)			
RT	1	69,9	71,5	71,9	71,4
	4	72,1	73,0	75,8	74,4
	6	70,9	72,5	73,2	72,1
70	1	71,2	72,4	73,0	72,7
	4	72,2	75,0	73,7	75,7
	6	72,7	73,1	76,1	76,5

Chemical digestion with H_2SO_4 was slightly improved with the increase of acid concentration, temperature and digestion time. This was in correlation with (Lopez-Abelairas et al., 2015). Beside the polymer recovery improvement, the increased acid concentration in all three conditions did not have a negative impact on thermal stability of PHB (Figure 20.). This confirmed the (Yu et al., 2005) hypothesis of acidic hydrolysis mechanism mentioned earlier in the literature review. Acidic digestion alone was not as good as alkali (Table 7. and 9.). This was probably due to a bad separation of impurities in the acidic pH. Harrison (1991) already reported the disadvantage of low pH when separation of soluble and insoluble cell constituents is desired. In the pH region between 2 and 5 the surface of bacterial cells is overall positively charged. On the other hand, the surface of PHB granules is negatively charged. This difference in the electric potential causes the formation of agglomerates in low pH buffers. For that reason, after the acidic digestion of FB2, pH was adjusted to 10 with NaOH to prevent precipitation of the impurities. Since polymer degradation wasn't observed after the acidic treatment, higher digestion temperature and H_2SO_4 concentration were tested as well. The results are shown in Table 10. and Figures 21. and 22.

Figure 20. H_2SO_4 concentration, incubation time and temperature impact on thermal stability of PHB in digested samples of FB1

Table 10. Effect of different digestion conditions with H_2SO_4 on PHB extraction from FB2 with the initial PHB content of 26.8 %, with 4% of solids in digestion solution and pH adjustment to 10 with 5 M NaOH

Chemical digestion	FB2	H_2SO_4 concentration		
		0,2	0,5	0,7
Digestion temperature [°C]	Digestion time [h]	PHB content (%)		
RT	4	27,6	28,1	28,1
	6	29,9	25,9	29,2
70	6	47,5	55,9	59,3
90	6	74,4	87,5	92,2

Figure 21. Comparison of PHB recovery from FB2 at 70°C with and without the pH adjustment after the chemical digestion

Figure 22. Comparison of PHB recovery from FB2 at 90°C with and without the pH adjustment after the chemical digestion

Increasing the digestion temperature and H₂SO₄ concentration, without pH adjustment that followed chemical digestion, furthermore improved PHB recovery without hydrolysing the polymer. pH adjustment after the acidic treatment to 10 with 5 M NaOH enhanced pellet precipitation, thus making the polymer separation more efficient. Beside separation, the PHB content in the recovered pellet significantly increased after the pH adjustment, meaning that the sulphuric acid alone cannot solubilise all of the NPCM. The additional PHB content increase after the pH adjustment was also observed by Yu and Chen (2006). On the other hand, PHB recovered after the pH adjustment had a lower thermal stability. This means that PHB, even in its crystalline form was still vulnerable to the attack of highly concentrated NaOH. Because of that, in the second stage screening, pH adjustment was performed with less concentrated NaOH.

4.4.3. Second stage screening

The goal of the second stage screening was to optimise chemical digestion conditions and implement a solvent polishing step. A schematic overview of the second stage screening is shown in Figure 23. Each number represents a different processing condition from which the best conditions were selected. The optimal condition had to yield the highest PHB content and/or lowest PHB degradation rate. This method was used for both FB1 and FB2.

Figure 23. Schematic overview of second stage screening

4.4.3.1. Second stage screening on FBI

In the first processing step, the highest PHB content was obtained by homogenization at 800 bar with 2 broth passages and SDS pretreatment at 0,025 g SDS/ g DM. Although the highest PHB content was observed after the digestion with 0.5 M NaOH, due to significant polymer degradation, 0,05 M and 0,075 M NaOH were tested instead. Acidic digestion was performed with 0,5 M H₂SO₄ at RT and 70°C for 6 h, with pH adjustment to 10 with 0,5 M NaOH after the digestion, since those conditions resulted PHB with the highest purity. After each digestion, the pellet was washed with either methanol or absolute ethanol. The obtained PHB concentrations are displayed in Table 11., for every combination of processing conditions.

Table 11. PHB content variation in combined processing steps of FB1

Second stage label	Processing step	Conditions	PHB content (%)
0	Starting broth	-	57,7
2	SDS + homogenization	0,025 g SDS/ g DM 800 bar 2 pass	70,2
2A	NaOH digestion	0,05 M 1 h RT	97,7
2AA		0,075 M 1 h RT	96,9
2Aa	NaOH digestion + solvent polishing	Absolute ethanol	98,0
2Ab		Methanol	98,3
2B	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion	0,5 M 6 h RT	73,4
		0,5 M 6 h RT after pH adjustment	93,7
2BB	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion	0,5 M 6 h 70°C	91,8
		0,5 M 6 h 70°C after pH adjustment	95,9
2BBa	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion + solvent polishing	Absolute ethanol	96,8
2BBb		Methanol	96,9

0,05 M NaOH was chosen as an optimal digestion agent for FB1 purification due to the highest PHB content obtained, mild processing conditions and marginal effect on polymer thermal stability (Figure 24.). In comparison with Choi and Lee (1999), who investigated PHB recovery from *E. Coli*, similar purity was obtained with 4 times less concentrated NaOH, when SDS induced homogenization was performed before alkaline digestion. Solvent polishing with both ethanol and methanol resulted in similar increase in PHB concentration, due to methanol's toxicity, ethanol was selected as better candidate for polishing.

Figure 24. Comparison of thermal stability of PHB purified from FB1 with different digestion agents

4.4.3.1. Second stage screening on FB2

Among the tested cell disruption conditions, the highest PHB content was obtained after the homogenization at 800 bar, with 2 broth passages and 0,05 g SDS / g DM. Slightly lower NaOH concentrations, 0,075 and 0,1 M at RT were chosen for alkali digestion for the same reason as mentioned in previous chapter. Acidic digestion was performed with 0,5 and 0,7 M H₂SO₄ at 90°C for 6 h since the highest PHB content was obtained under those conditions. Solvent polishing screening was again tested with absolute ethanol and methanol. The obtained PHB concentrations are displayed in Table 12. for every combination of processing conditions.

Table 12. PHB content variation in combined processing steps of FB2

Second stage label	Processing step	Conditions	PHB content (%)
0	Start	-	26,8
2	SDS + homogenization	0,05 g SDS/ g DM 800 bar 2 pass	38,3
2A	NaOH digestion	0,075 M 1 h RT	65,4
2AA		0,1 M 1 h RT	76,3
2Aa	NaOH digestion + solvent polishing	Absolute ethanol	77,4
2Ab		Methanol	78,9
2B	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion	0,5 M 6 h 90°C	69,2
		0,5 M 6 h 90°C after pH adjustment	87,3
2BB	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion	0,7 M 6h 90°C	74,5
		0,7 M 6h 90°C after pH adjustment	93,5
2BBa	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion	Absolute ethanol	95,1
2BBb		Methanol	97,2

Unlike FB1, the optimal digestion agent for FB2 was 0,7 M H₂SO₄ at 90°C for 6 h. This may be due to much higher NPCM content in the starting broth, as well as because of the difference in cell physiology of the two bacterial strains. 0,1 M NaOH was not strong enough to dissolve majority of NPCM, while concentrations higher than 0,1 M had a negative effect on thermal stability of PHB.

4.5. Solid/liquid separation

A solid/liquid separation step is required after the water washing steps, after homogenization and after chemical digestion for the removal of water-soluble cellular debris. For that purpose, two different separation methods were evaluated during the downstream processing of FB1, centrifugation and ultrafiltration.

4.5.1. Solid/liquid separation after SDS treatment and homogenization

To test whether separation by centrifugation would be efficient on the large-scale disc stack centrifuges at BBEPP, homogenized broth was poured in a 50 mL falcon and centrifuged

for 1 min at 4700 g. Since the pellet was not stable, centrifugation time had to be increased to 10 min. The pellet was then resuspended in RO-water and centrifugation was repeated. Pictures of centrifuged samples after the 1st centrifugation and 1st washing step are shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Centrifuged sample of FB1 after the SDS treatment and homogenization (left) and the 1st washing step (right)

As an alternative for separating the homogenized FB1 broth (2 L), ultrafiltration was performed with a ceramic 300 kDa membrane. 2 diafiltrations were performed in RO-water to retentate ration of 1:1. The flux during filtration was 30,52 L/hm² with a feed pressure ranging from 0,4-0,7 barg. After diafiltrations, 500 mL of retentate was recovered. A 5 mL sample of the 300 kDa filtrate was centrifuged at 14 000 g force, and no pellet was observed. The PHB content was compared between the two solid liquid separation techniques and is displayed in Table 13.

Table 13. PHB content in the dry samples after centrifugation or UF filtration

FB1	PHB content (%)
Centrifuged pellet	76,6
300 kDa retentate	80,4

UF turned out to be a more promising technique for solid/liquid separation, as fluxes were high. On the other hand, long sedimentation time is required for centrifugation, making it less practical on the industrial scale.

4.5.2. Solid/liquid separation after NaOH chemical digestion

The same procedure was repeated after the chemical digestion step. This time, samples had to be centrifuged for 20 min to obtain a stable pellet (Figure 26.). The pellet was washed twice with RO-water to removed supernatant ratio of 1:1. For every washing step, 5 mL of obtained supernatant was recentrifuged at 14 000 g to check whether losses occurred towards the supernatant (Figure 27.)

Figure 26. Centrifuged sample of FB1 after the NaOH chemical digestion

Figure 27. Recentrifuged supernatant after water washing steps

It was apparent that with every water washing step, using centrifugation as a pellet separation method, solids (including PHB) were lost towards the supernatant phase.

On the other hand, a clear filtrate was obtained using 300 kDa UF filtration. The flux during filtration and both diafiltrations was 37,07 L/hm² with a feed pressure ranging from 0,3 - 0,5 barg. Starting feed (solution after the chemical digestion) got concentrated 3 times. The PHB content was again compared between the two solid liquid separation techniques and is displayed in Table 14.

Table 14. PHB content in the dry samples after centrifugation and UF filtration

FB1	PHB content (%)
Centrifuged pellet	98,8
300 kDa retentate	97,5

Comparable PHB purities were obtained after the washing steps performed with both separation techniques. Centrifuges with high sigma factor will be required if centrifugation would be performed on large-scale since very long centrifugation time was necessary for separating the pellet from the liquid phase. On the other hand, high fluxes were obtained during separation via UF, which means that this separation method will be more applicable on the industrial-scale.

4.6. Repetition of complete DSP steps for FB1 and FB2

The best individual process steps were compiled into a full DSP process, and fresh samples were completely processed using the developed DSP process. This was done to validate the current findings, and to calculate the recovery yields. The results are shown in Table 15. and 16.

Table 15. Recovery yield and PHB content in the developed DSP process for FB1

Step number	Processing step	Conditions	PHB content (%)	Recovery yield (%) of the individual step
0	Start	-	65,0	100
1	SDS + homogenization	0,025 g SDS/ g DM 800bar 2 pass	74,9	92,3
2	NaOH digestion	0,05 M 1 h RT	99,1	92,01
3a	Solvent polishing	Absolute ethanol	99,7	74,2
3b		Methanol	99,8	86,8
Overall recovery yield (%) (1, 2, 3a)				71,11

Homogenization in combination with SDS showed sufficient performance in cell disruption efficiency, PHB content in the solid phase increased to 75 %. This was also evident in the increased brittleness and the change in colour of the dry samples after this step (Figure 28.). The losses generated during homogenization were caused by so-called general processing losses – some amount of the product stuck to the inner surface of the processing unit. These losses were considered as constant and were mostly connected to the efficiency of rinsing. Apart from that, the decrease in recovery yield may also be caused by inefficient solid separation by centrifugation during the two washing steps that followed homogenization.

After the NaOH digestion, PHB content increased to 99,1 %. A similar result was reported by Lo et al. (2011) who purified PHB from recombinant *E. coli* with the combination of homogenization, SDS treatment and alkali digestion. In comparison with their research, the same purity was obtained but with much lower concentrations of SDS and NaOH.

Solvent polishing with both ethanol and methanol additionally increased PHB content but had a big impact on the product recovery. Since washing with ethanol and methanol requires ATEX conditions on the large scale, which increases capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operating expenses (OPEX), execution of this step is optional depending on the required end product purity.

Figure 28. Dry FB1 samples containing PHB after each processing step (Table 13.)

Table 16. Recovery yield and PHB content in the developed DSP process for FB2

Step number	Processing step	Conditions	PHB content (%)	Recovery yield (%)
0	Start	-	26,8	100
1	SDS + homogenization	0,05 g SDS/ g DM 800bar 2 pass	45,5	93,6
2	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion + pH adjustment to 10 after digestion (using 0,5 M NaOH)	0,7 M 6 h 90°C	88,1	76,17
3a	Solvent polishing	Absolute ethanol	91,6	79,8
3b		Methanol	94,2	83,5
Overall recovery yield (%) (1, 2, 3b)				53,27

A similar recovery yield was obtained after the first processing step in comparison with the FB1. On the other hand, acidic digestion resulted with much lower recovery yield. Lopez-Abelairas et al. (2015) reported similar recovery (79 %) but with much higher purity (98 %) after the acidic digestion at 80°C with 3,5 % v/v sulphuric acid for 6 h. Reason for that is probably the additional bleaching step they performed after the pH adjustment (with 3 % sodium hypochlorite solution for 1 h). Beside general processing losses, lower recovery can be attributed to high temperatures that were used and pH adjustment with 0,5 M NaOH which may lead to polymer degradation to soluble degradation products, such as crotonic acid. To prove that, additional analysis should be performed in the future to check which degradation products are formed during digestion.

With the methanol polishing step PHB content increased to 94,2 %, this difference was also visible in the dry PHB sample that appeared whiter after the final polishing (Figure 29.). A somewhat lower PHB content and recovery yield was obtained after ethanol washing.

Figure 29. Dry FB2 samples containing PHB after each processing step (Table 14.)

4.5.1. Comparison of thermal properties of purified PHB from FB1 and FB2 with chloroform extracted PHB from FB1

The thermal degradation of PHB purified from FB1 took place in the same temperature range as PHB extracted with chloroform (Figure 30.). Meaning that the thermal stability of FB1 end product was the same as of PHB obtained using the control extraction method. On the other hand, PHB purified from FB2 (using acidic digestion) showed slightly reduced thermal stability. Since sulphuric acid in concentration ranges between 0,05-2 M does not degrade PHB (Yu et al., 2005), (Figure 20.) partial hydrolysis was most probably caused by 0,5 M NaOH that was used for pH adjustment. This means that the pH adjustment step after the acidic digestion still has to be optimised.

Figure 30. Thermal degradation comparison between PHB purified from FB1 and FB2 with chloroform extracted PHB from FB1

4.6. Application of the best processing conditions in purification of PHB from FB3

Since the quantity of FB3 was not sufficient for the complete homogenization and chemical digestion conditions screening (Table 5.), the best observed conditions in purification of PHB from FB1 and FB2 were tested on FB3. The PHB content and recovery yield for each processing step is shown in Table 17.

Table 17. Recovery yield and PHB content in the developed DSP process for FB3

Step number	Processing step	Conditions	PHB content (%)	Recovery yield (%)
0	Start		45,4	100
1	SDS + homogenization	0,05 g SDS/ g DM 800bar 2 pass	56,6	96,6
2A	NaOH digestion	0,05 M NaOH	91,2	94,9
2B	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion	0,7 M 6 h 90°C	96,5	90,9
3Aa	NaOH digestion + solvent polishing	Absolute ethanol	94,2	88,5
3Ba	H ₂ SO ₄ digestion + solvent polishing	Absolute ethanol	99,2	90,8
Overall recovery yield (%) (1, 2B, 3Ba)				78,3

The recovery yield after the first purification step was slightly better than those obtained after processing FB1 and FB2. After the SDS treatment and homogenization, the mixed culture broth turned into a dense slurry because of the release of intracellular compounds such as nucleic acids and phospholipids. Since centrifugation of the broth was not feasible and consequently, not performed, the losses that most probably take place in the pellet separation during the washing steps were avoided here. On the other hand, UF could not be tested because of the small broth volume. Between acidic and alkali digestion, a slightly higher PHB content was obtained after the digestion with sulphuric acid, although the recovery yield was higher after NaOH digestion. An ethanol washing step additionally increased PHB content by 3% in both acidic and alkali digested pellets. The picture of dry pellet after each step is shown in Figure 30. Since the PHB content and total recovery in the end samples is relatively close, thermal properties of purified PHB were analysed in order to conclude which digestion method is better (Figure 31.).

Figure 31. Dry FB3 samples containing PHB after each processing step

Figure 32. Thermal degradation difference between samples digested with NaOH and H₂SO₄

The degradation temperature of PHB purified via acidic digestion was lower than PHB purified by weak alkali digestion. This is most probably caused by the partial PHB hydrolysis that occurred during pH adjustment with 0,5 M NaOH. The same change in thermal degradation temperature was observed after the acidic digestion of FB2.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the obtained results in this thesis, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Composition of the starting fermentation broths was determined: FB1 contained PHB in a concentration of 64 % w/w, FB2 contained PHB in a concentration of 26,8 % w/w and FB3 contained PHB in a concentration of 45,4 % w/w.
2. The highest PHB purity for FB1 (99,8 %) and overall recovery yield (71,11 %) was obtained with following DSP steps: homogenization at 800 bar, with 2 broth passages and 0,025 g SDS/g DM, chemical digestion with 0,05 M NaOH for 1 h at RT and final washing with methanol in pellet to solvent ratio of 1:20 for 3 h.
3. The highest PHB purity for FB2 (94,2 %) and overall recovery yield (53,27 %) was obtained with following DSP steps: homogenization at 800 bar, with 2 broth passages and 0,05 g SDS/g DM, chemical digestion with 0,7 M H₂SO₄ for 6 h at 90°C, pH adjustment to 10 with 0,5 M NaOH and final washing with methanol in pellet to solvent ratio of 1:20 for 3 h.
- 4.. The highest PHB purity for FB3 (99,2 %) and overall recovery yield (78,3 %) was obtained with following DSP steps: homogenization at 800 bar, with 2 broth passages and 0,05 g SDS/g DM, chemical digestion with 0,7 M H₂SO₄ for 6 h at 90°C, pH adjustment to 10 with 0,5 M NaOH and final washing with ethanol in pellet to solvent ratio of 1:20 for 3 h.
5. The increase in NaOH concentration during chemical digestion resulted in an increase of the PHB purity, but it had a negative impact on the polymer thermal stability when concentrations higher than 0,1 M were used. Prolonged digestion time (> 1 h) and higher incubation temperatures (> 25°C) didn't improve polymer recovery.
6. The increase in H₂SO₄ concentration, incubation time and temperature increased the PHB concentration and didn't have negative impact on the thermal stability of purified PHB.
7. pH adjustment to 10 with 0,5 M NaOH that followed acidic digestion improved separation of impurities but it also caused slight PHB degradation.
8. Higher PHB concentrations and recovery yields were obtained when methanol was used as a polishing solvent for FB1 and FB2 in comparison with ethanol.

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1. List of abbreviations

3-HB	3-hydroxybutyric acid
3-HV	3-hydroxyvaleric acid
ATPS	aqueous two-phase system
BBEPP	Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant
CA	crotonic acid
CAPEX	capital expenditures
DM (%S)	percentage of dry matter
DSP	downstream process
GC-MS	gas chromatography – mass spectrometry
HA	hydroxy acid
HPH	high pressure homogenization
MMC	mixed microbial consortia
NPCM	non PHA cell mass
OH ⁻	hydroxyl anion
OPEX	operating expenses
PCL	polycaprolactone
PE	polyethylene
PHA	polyhydroxyalkanoates
PHB	polyhydroxybutyrate
PLA	polylactic acid
PP	polypropylene
RT	room temperature ($\pm 25^{\circ}\text{C}$)
SCF	supercritical fluids
SDS	sodium dodecyl sulphate
TG(A)	thermogravimetric (analysis)

2. PHA identification in different fermentation broths

Figure 33. GC-MS chromatogram of FB1 broth showing 3-HB and benzoic acid peak

Figure 34. GC-MS chromatogram of FB2 broth showing 3-HB and benzoic acid peak

Figure 35. GC-MS chromatogram of FB3 broth showing 3-HB and benzoic acid peak